

New Education Technology Application Status and Dilemma in Primary School: A Bangladesh School Perspective in Context to China

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

1. Aim of the Research

The present study will benefit students because they will be able to understand their educational technology and how it can help them learn more effectively, and teachers will recognize the importance of technology in

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ABSTRACT

Perhaps the most powerful influence on today's educational landscape is technology. Many schools are supporting increased levels of technology in the classroom by providing hardware like tablets and computers, improving internet connectivity, and implementing computer literacy programs for both teachers and students. Although most teachers recognize the value of educational technology, they often find it difficult to integrate new technologies smoothly and effectively. Technology integration presents significant challenges to educators at all levels of school systems, from the acquisition of new technology equipment to the adaptation of curricula and teaching techniques to incorporate new educational tools. The goal of this chapter is to present common challenges that educators face when attempting to integrate technology into the classroom, as well as potential solutions. Current and future educators, school administrators, and educational technology researchers should all benefit from a closer look at these issues.

Keywords: NEW EDUCATION TECHNOLOGY; DIGITAL BANGLADESH; ICT

the classroom while teaching.

1.1 Introduction

Bangladesh's phenomenal economic growth over the last few decades has drawn scholarly attention to the country's relative performance in various spheres. However, there has been little analysis of their integration of new technology in educational systems. This is a critical research gap, given the importance of education in economic and social development, and the fact that these two countries have the world's two largest education systems. Evaluating their relative achievements and challenges will shed light on the efficacy of these two countries' various education strategies, not only for their own benefit but also for the benefit of the rest of the developing world.

Over the last two decades, technological advancements have forever changed the face of education. Revolutionary advances in ICT, particularly disciplines related to computers, mobile phones, and the Internet, have sparked a renaissance in educational technology.

After the development of this decade, modern information technology teaching has been popularized to primary schools at all levels as an important auxiliary means of classroom teaching in schools. All types of education are gradually incorporating modern information technology. The efficiency of teacher teaching has greatly improved, from class preparation to class teaching, so that students can feel more perceptual, multi-angle, and multi-level in limited time and space. It not only encourages teachers to retrain themselves, but it also keeps up with the times and moves away from the innovative mountain teaching and modern information teaching paths. It is very important in comparing the quality and quantity of teaching evaluations.

2. Literature Review

The purpose of this paper is to discuss the use of educational technology in Bangladeshi primary schools, as well as the issues that arise from it. The classroom environment, as well as student-to-student and student-to-teacher interaction, was also highlighted. When planning a learning environment using technology, it is critical to consider the characteristics, abilities, and experience of learners as individuals or as a group in order to ensure the effectiveness of teaching environments. Considering group or individual learners' characteristics, competence, and experiences throughout the process of planning learning environments is critical for the effectiveness of teaching environments. Teachers are unaware of a student's learning style, which is crucial information for a teacher to have. A teacher will not be able to teach properly if they do not know the student's learning style, and it is obvious that the student will not understand the material. As previously stated, each student has a unique learning style that is determined by birth. They don't always understand what the teacher is saying because the teacher isn't teaching them in their preferred learning style. For example, one student excels at writing while another excels at listening. The person who is good at writing can memorize by writing, while the other is used to memorizing by carefully listening. There is no point in

teaching if the teacher does not allow time for students to take notes or if the teacher does not learn about the student's learning style.

2.1 Chinas New Education Technology

When Chairman Deng Xiaoping visited a secondary school in Beijing around three decades ago, he said, "Education should be geared toward modernization, globalization, and future construction." The "educational modernization movement," which focused primarily on the adoption and application of instructional technology, was a direct response to this assertion. Chairman Deng Xiaoping said three decades ago, when visiting a Beijing secondary school, that "education should be geared toward modernization, globalization, and future construction." The "educational modernization movement" was a linear response to this remark, focusing primarily on the adoption and application of educational technologies, as well as "modernizing" education to achieve great-leap-forward advancement.

The "Modernizing" of education is becoming increasingly important to Chinese government and educational groups. By establishing new education technology literacy training programs at teacher education institutions, the government has paid special emphasis to preparing pre-service teachers and in-service teachers to integrate new education technology into their classroom instruction. In China, more and more teachers are being given opportunities to use innovative educational technologies in their classrooms. It is not exaggerated to say that instructors' access to educational technology is no longer a barrier. As a result, both in industrialized areas and in China's western rural areas, technology in education has made great progress and successes. Technology's effectiveness in education has dramatically enhanced, instructors' technological competency has been strengthened, and the traditional teaching and learning approach has been significantly modified. Educational technology has played an important role in education and is a key component of educational modernization. ICT is known to both teachers and students, and they want to use it to help their teaching and learning.

Despite the good picture painted by numerous reports, few teachers use ICT in their classrooms on a regular basis, and the impact of ICT on existing curricula is minimal. Schoolteachers are unable to use Internet-based resources and instead "use computers as television sets." The attempt to integrate technology into teaching is riddled with inconsistencies. It is proposed that researchers assist instructors in developing their ICT beliefs in Chinese elementary and secondary schools. Modern educational reform should include a deeper understanding and development of teachers' beliefs. As previously stated, experts in Western contexts believe that instructors' intrinsic variables may play a significant impact in technology integration. This concept serves as a foundation for the current study, although it is framed in a Chinese cultural framework.

3. Method of Research

In the research, a study of Bangladeshi students was conducted, as well as the application of new

students in schools. Another goal of the study is to discover the dilemmas that students and teachers face when using new technology. Successful learning style programming necessitates the support of teachers and their positive attitude toward students. Teachers have a role to play in increasing students' technological proficiency. According to the findings, some students are visual learners, while others are audio learners, and still others are kinesthetic learners; however, teachers must successfully identify each student individually. Learners will benefit from knowing their individual learning styles. They will be able to learn more effectively because of this. Furthermore, school officials, as well as teachers and parents, must take steps to implement the use of new technology in classrooms.

3.1 Literature based case study

While this review focuses on literature from developing countries like China, it also draws upon extensive research from developing countries as Bangladesh. We hope this literature-based case study will advance the knowledge base of how technology can be used to support education, outline key areas for new experimental research, and help drive improvements to the policies, programs, and structures that contribute to successful teaching and learning.

4. Analyzing the Finding

4.1 Application of Distance Learning

The Distance Education System in primary School has been in operation since 2019 after the global pandemic started. After trial exploration, the teachers at School have tried to get to the air classroom for the first time. The school has set up the distance education machine room, set up the distance education group, download the system to back up the course resources, carve up the Flash Drive, take grade as the sequence to do the teaching resources and the effective use of the teacher, many teachers have found the suitable material from a large number of distance education resources, or make use of existing courseware to modify, become the multimedia courseware suitable for their preparation content, effectively improve the teaching quality, make all teachers try to the best. At the same time, the Office of Distance Education announced the schedule for the opening of the "Online Class" in all subject areas in due course, so that students in primary schools would also share the situation of excellent teachers in model schools in developed areas. Not only is there an extra way of learning, but also allows teachers to learn the advanced teaching experience of excellent teachers without leaving their homes.

This is the basic status quo of our teachers' initial use of modern information. Although there are many areas for improvement in online education in terms of coverage and utilization efficiency, it makes teachers realize that modern information teaching technology has penetrated classroom teaching, widened students' horizons and accelerated teachers' sense of urgency to participate in modern educational technology learning.

4.2 Application and Analysis of Multimedia Classroom

Since 2010, schools have established a multimedia classroom, although the equipment is primitive and backward now, it was a treasure at that time. Not to mention the students, even the teachers are new when they see it. At the beginning, the full screen English makes people step backward, so the utilization rate is too low and can only be regarded as high-grade furnishings. Later, after computer teachers refitted the Win8 system and established a diskless workstation, they really realized the man-machine interaction mode with friendly interface, but dial-up Internet access has not been realized. Students and teachers can only learn basic desktop application, practice typing and play some games. Utilization has not improved much. In 2014, after many efforts, the school finally updated the hardware of the computer room and established a new modern multi-functional multimedia classroom with 845 motherboard chip level and full network coverage. The school spent great efforts to open the multimedia computer room. From grade 3 to grade 6, under the guidance of professional computer teachers, the school realized two computer classes a week. Now the systematic implementation of the organic integration of modern information education and traditional teaching in mountainous areas makes students freely contact with the outside world. Modern information teaching network has large capacity and more information, improves teaching efficiency, can better stimulate students' interest, enrich students' learning life, lays a solid foundation for students' future computer application, and speeds up teachers' participation The urgency of modern educational technology learning.

4.3 Implementation of Digital Bangladesh

The "Digital Bangladesh" project in schools has been officially used since 2010. The "Digital Bangladesh" project is another leap in the application of modern information technology in school, which is a qualitative leap in multimedia teaching. If the first two application modes have greatly promoted students' learning and the reform of classroom teaching, the "Digital Bangladesh" project has truly integrated modern information technology into students' daily life, realized the use of network resources for education and teaching in ordinary classrooms, and realized the normalized and effective utilization of modern educational information resources, Urge teachers to actively adapt to the new mode of classroom resource application under the condition of modern information, so as to achieve twice the result with half the effort in teaching.

All classes in school have realized the effective utilization of "Digital Bangladesh communication", adopted a unified platform, integrated video separation, integrated operation of computer and projector, whole school control of audio broadcasting, specification of steel lecture table, and the use of a full set of equipment has realized network automatic management.

The "Digital Bangladesh" project has brought many new changes to teaching in primary school. Many teachers consciously try to use modern educational technology for audio-visual teaching, and the utilization rate of video, voice and courseware has increased significantly. The construction and use of "Digital Bangladesh" have promoted the transformation of teachers' lesson preparation mode from traditional manual individual lesson preparation to collective and network lesson preparation and sharing mode, it realizes the

sharing means of lesson preparation resources for many students and teachers, combines traditional means with modern teaching methods, changes backward teaching means and realizes the optimization of classroom efficiency. Multimedia assisted instruction is used in the classroom teaching of an open class and fed back to each teacher's study, life, and work.

4.2 Usage of Smart Device

At present, teachers at school use the information platform of school smart to effectively communicate with families in real time, which greatly facilitates parents to timely and accurately understand students' learning and conduct. Teachers use the group sending function of notice and message most on the school smart platform, such as group sending school notice, homework and so on. Some parents pay special attention to students' homework information. Teachers can add the purpose of daily homework, Item requirements, counseling process, etc. to the homework information. It is believed these contents are very popular with parents.

5. Dilemma and Suggestions

5.1 Maintenance on Daily Basis

In daily work, there are large and small fault problems in computing room, distance education room and digital Bangladesh communication project. Some problems arise from teachers' use skills, and more teachers with professional maintenance knowledge in computer and network are needed to solve them. As the daily management and user of modern information technology, Front line teachers and technical maintenance personnel still need to go through many "checkpoints". The primary condition for the normal use of equipment is to solve the problem of maintenance. The technical expertise of maintenance personnel directly affects whether each teacher and classroom can normally use multimedia courseware and network. If they blindly ask for help from off campus technicians in terms of hardware technology troubleshooting, the use of modern information technology in schools will produce unnecessary cost burden. Therefore, the school must make good arrangements for technicians in computer and network maintenance, and arrange the maintenance of technicians, which is also a key point of this work. The maintenance work of technicians shall be included in the workload as class hours and institutionalized in quantitative assessment. Only when the maintenance personnel keep up and the technology is excellent, the normal operation of software and hardware will not be affected, and the application of modern information technology can be effectively carried out in rural schools.

The maintenance work shall be divided in detail and checked one by one, so as to be rapid and effective. We should also carry out special training for teachers in the gap between work, so that teachers can develop correct use methods and reduce the burden of maintenance personnel, so as to make the modern information equipment of the school better serve teaching. Therefore, I strongly suggest that rural schools must establish a technical maintenance team with excellent quality, qualified technology and a certain amount of energy. It

is directly managed by the distance education office in a unified group, and the team leader is selected according to individual and specialty to form a maintenance team, such as network maintenance team, hardware maintenance team and software maintenance team. Group troubleshooting, formulate regular troubleshooting mechanism, do a good job in personnel division and troubleshooting record registration, and summarize and report common faults. Carry out daily summary group work in an orderly manner to achieve twice the result with half the effort. At the same time, the maintenance personnel must have the spirit of ownership, delimit the duty rounds, make judgment at any time, respond quickly, and handle correctly. Let teachers rest assured and happy to use.

5.2 Training of Teachers

In the use of modern information technology, teacher training is a key problem to be solved. For various reasons, teachers' age characteristics, personal preferences and cognitive levels are different. Therefore, the school should do a good job in the all-round training of teachers. During the preliminary training, a questionnaire can be used. According to the survey results, the teachers at the school are divided into three groups of high school and low school for group teaching and training, to train teachers' relevant professional knowledge.

The training can combine explanation and demonstration to explain the common skills in the use of modern teaching information technology and learn simple troubleshooting, Keep records of problem feedback. Conditional schools can also take the use of modern information technology as a hard index for open course evaluation. Teachers with new breakthroughs in multimedia teaching methods should promote the whole school as a small model to promote teaching and research activities to a deeper level.

The retraining of teachers includes not only the basic training of ordinary teachers, but also the retraining of computer teachers. Improve technical means to better serve school network teaching.

5.3 Resources and Management

The school-based resource base is a gradual filling process. It will become more and more abundant, let teachers learn from each other, make more use of modern educational technology network teaching resources, and effectively integrate the aesthetic education research in combination with the content of research, so as to make the practice of school-based teaching materials and courses in rural primary schools more wonderful under the application of modern educational technology, Teachers with outstanding research contributions should also be given some material incentives.

6. Conclusion

Good teaching and research activities are the foundation for better utilization of new technology, which in turn promotes the continuous improvement of teaching effect, which will form a virtuous circle in the teaching chain of schools and is an organic unity of teaching. Therefore, it is necessary to deal with the

teaching research of the integration of information technology and discipline under the condition of new technology. In short, primary schools in Bangladesh must seize the opportunity of the times and construct appropriate modern teaching methods, to maximize equity and justice in school education and serve every child in the mountainous areas.

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